

HEROISM BY EARLY EPIC AUTHORS

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Abstract. This article examines how bravery is portrayed in early epic literature through an analysis of works by writers like Homer, Virgil, and the unidentified authors of "Beowulf" and "The Epic of Gilgamesh." It looks at what it means to be a hero, the cultural setting, and these legendary heroes' lasting influence. The purpose of this essay is to present a thorough knowledge of how early epics inspired subsequent literature and developed the idea of heroism. The Old Testament and Greek mythology have both had a major impact on the advancement of Western civilization. The legendary Trojan War warriors have inspired countless writers and painters, and they still motivate brave people to embark on daring expeditions today.

Key words: epic literature, heroism, epic authors, civilization, bravery, honor and sacrifice.

ГЕРОИЗМ РАННИХ АВТОРОВ ЭПОСА

Аннотация. В этой статье рассматривается, как храбрость изображалась в ранней эпической литературе, на основе анализа произведений таких писателей, как Гомер, Вергилий и неизвестные авторы "Беовульфа" и "Эпоса о Гильгамеше". В нем рассказывается о том, что значит быть героем, о культурной среде и о том, какое влияние оказали эти легендарные герои. Цель этого эссе - дать исчерпывающее представление о том, как ранние эпосы вдохновляли последующую литературу и развивали идею героизма. Ветхий Завет и греческая мифология оказали огромное влияние на развитие западной цивилизации. Легендарные воины Троянской войны вдохновили бесчисленное множество писателей и художников, и они по-прежнему побуждают отважных людей отправляться в дерзкие экспедиции и по сей день.

Ключевые слова: эпическая литература, героизм, авторы эпосов, цивилизация, храбрость, честь и самопожертвование.

INTRODUCTION

Heroism has been a major theme in literature since the dawn of narrative. The early epic poets defined the concept of a hero with their vivid narratives and fanciful characters. These ancient texts provide insight into the values and beliefs of their diverse communities as well as

timeless instances of bravery, honor, and sacrifice. Through an analysis of the characters and narratives of notable epic writers, this article delves into the definition and celebration of heroism in such works. The "heroic" existence was the subject of epic poetry, folklore, and philosophers' attention until recently. It was undoubtedly at the core of the ancients' conception of life. The word "life," which is intentionally capitalized here, refers to the perspective of a holy and profane world-universe existence that blurs the lines between the legendary and the everyday. It is indeed a "religious" worldview, if that is how it is named. Religion and life were frequently synonymous in the ancient world. Likewise, the idea of "heroism" was used to describe whether or not an individual's deeds were heroic, depending on their religious or philosophical outlook on life. The idea of heroism in the Western tradition changed over the millennia of ancient civilization. It started with the Greeks' natural courage, as told in Homer's epic poem *The Iliad*, and developed into the Stoic Roman idea presented in Marcus Aurelius' *Meditations*. In the end, it resulted in the early Christian mystic understanding of bravery, which is shown in pieces like "The Passion of Saint Perpetua." The purpose of this little article is to examine how the antiquated notion of the heroic life changed throughout time and in those three works, as well as to seek for any recurrent themes or concepts.

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Homer and the Greek Heroic Ideal- Homer's "Odyssey" and "Iliad" are famous pieces that perfectly capture Greek bravery. Achilles and Odysseus, the two primary characters of these epics, each symbolize a different kind of bravery. Achilles, with his incredible strength and fighting prowess, represents the perfect warrior pursuing everlasting glory. His physical prowess and unwavering bravery in battle are characteristics of his heroism. On the other side, Odysseus is a fantastic illustration of cunning, intelligence, and bravery. His journey from Troy to his home is full of obstacles that test his wits and resilience, exhibiting a unique form of heroism that places equal weight on mental toughness and physical strength. The stories of Odysseus's adventures in the Trojan War and his heroic return to Ithaca found in both *The Iliad* and *The Odyssey* are notable examples of bravery, cunning, and courage.[1] Unlike other well-known Trojan War heroes like Achilles or Hector, Odysseus's reputation is more closely linked to his diplomatic skills, leadership qualities, sharp intellect, and cunning than it is to his military ability. As a result, he is regarded as Troy's most rational leader.

Virgil's Aeneid and Roman Virtues- Virgil's "Aeneid" describes a hero who is both a warrior and a devoted leader. Three Roman traits are personified by Aeneas: *gravitas* (seriousness), *virtus* (courage), and *pietas* (duty). Unlike the more individualistic Greek heroes, Aeneas's heroism

is characterized by his loyalty to his people and the will of the gods. He established Rome, proving his tenacity and sacrifice and solidifying the Roman notion of heroism as selfless service to a greater cause. The Aeneid's author, Virgil, composed his epic poem as propaganda. Virgil was called upon to support the cause of rigorous moral reform during the reign of Augustus, the emperor, at the time the Aeneid was composed. Virgil, who was regarded as the greatest poet of the day, wrote the Aeneid, a story of honor, duty, and loss. Emphasizing duty as the primary virtue of Rome, Virgil crafted the archetypal Roman man, Pius Aeneas, who is prepared to give up all for his devotion to Rome.[2] In addition to being the quintessential Roman, Aeneas was also, so myth tells us, Augustus' ancestor and the one who founded Rome. Some have claimed that Virgil is condemning Aeneas all throughout the poem, pointing to several instances in which he willfully ignores the people he ought to care about; nevertheless, these critics are misinterpreting Virgil's motivations.

The Epic of Gilgamesh: A Quest for Immortality- One of the first known literary works, "The Epic of Gilgamesh," introduces Gilgamesh, a ruler who at first personifies the paradigm of a tyrant-hero. Throughout the epic, his bravery changes, going from daring adventures to a deep search for enlightenment and immortality. Through his path of self-discovery and enlightenment, Gilgamesh portrays heroism as a reflection of the human condition and the search for meaning. The epic begins in the majestic city of Uruk, where we are first introduced to Gilgamesh, the epic's legendary hero. Gilgamesh is depicted in the book as being two thirds god and one third mortal, endowed with great power and intelligence, but frequently abusing these attributes.[3] Gilgamesh's character's dualism serves as a metaphor for the complexity present in all people.

Beowulf and the Anglo-Saxon Hero "Beowulf"- heroic poem in the Anglo-Saxon style, showcasing the hero's bravery in the face of fearsome beasts. Beowulf's strength, loyalty, and leadership are qualities that define his heroism. The Anglo-Saxon heroic code, which values courage, fidelity to one's lord and kin, and the defense of one's nation, is highlighted throughout the epic.[4] Beowulf epitomizes the ultimate heroic ideal of self-sacrifice for the greater good in his final act of bravery, where he sacrifices his life to fight a dragon.

CONCLUSION

Early epic literature's diverse yet connected portrayals of valor reflect the ideals and standards of the cultures in which they were produced. From the valor of Achilles and the cunning of Odysseus to the love of Aeneas and the life-altering adventure of Gilgamesh, these heroes have left a lasting mark on the literary world. Because of their ability to illustrate the complexities of heroism and inspire many generations to learn more about the ideas of bravery, honor, and

sacrifice, these epics have persisted. These ancient tales show how the heroic ideal endures and are still valuable and inspirational for us as readers in the modern day.

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